

EFFECT OF MEAN STRESS ON THE NOTCHED AND UNNOTCHED
LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF CROSSPLY COMPOSITES

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The technical literature on the fatigue characteristics of composite materials, particularly glass fibre reinforced plastics, is growing at a fast rate. But it still lags behind the advances in the structural applications of these modern materials.

While a significant amount of research is being done on the various aspects of composite fatigue behaviour, the designer cannot yet get much important information for composites, unlike in the case of metals. To cite only a few examples, the effect of stress concentrations and the effect of mean stress on the fatigue behaviour of composites are not fully understood. The designer needs information, even if it is only empirical, such as the range of notch sensitivity and a design criterion similar to the Goodman or Soderberg criterion.

Until very recently, composites, particularly glass fiber reinforced plastics, were considered to have a lower notch sensitivity compared to metals. This notch insensitivity was attributed to the progressive damage at the notch root and the consequent blunting of the notch. But the author has, in a series of papers, shown that while the above may be the general behaviour, composites may also exhibit two extremes of behaviour: the notch sensitivity may be very close to one (if the polymeric matrix itself is very brittle) or the notch sensitivity may be negative (if the polymeric matrix is ductile and exhibits a negative notch sensitivity by itself).

The notch-strengthening effect, mentioned above, has been observed in static tensile and low-cycle fatigue tests where the stress-ratio (ratio of minimum to maximum stress in the cycle) was kept constant. Another valid definition of notch sensitivity is on the basis of equal mean stress. Besides, the effect of mean stress itself is important as the alternating fatigue strength (mean stress zero) and static tensile strength are easier to obtain compared to the fluctuating fatigue strength. In the case of metals, R-M diagrams and empirical relations such as Goodman or Soderberg criterion are well known. But similar information for composites is not available.

In the present investigation, results based on a systematic investigation of the effect of mean stress on the notched and unnotched low-cycle fatigue strength are reported. When the final paper is written, over five hundred specimens would have been tested. For design purposes, composites can be

divided into three groups: those which exhibit a low notch sensitivity, those which exhibit a high notch sensitivity and those which exhibit a negative notch sensitivity. In this paper the first and third materials are dealt with by using the same composite sheet at 0° and 45° - since there is a strengthening effect at 45° in the particular case.

Experiments are in full swing (ten to fifteen specimens are being tested every day) and it is expected that R-M (alternating stress vs mean stress for a particular life) diagrams will be obtained for 0° (low notch sensitivity) and 45° (significant negative notch sensitivity) orientations. The notch sensitivity will be determined on the basis of the same mean stress and compared with that determined previously on the basis of same stress-ratio. The extension range in the stress-controlled fatigue tests is monitored in each test. Very interestingly, while the extension limits keep on increasing, the extension range stabilizes - both for 0° and 45° specimens; previous work by the author dealt with a material for which the 45° orientation did not exhibit a stabilized extension range. Preliminary results indicate that there is a definite relation between the extension range and the alternating component of stress, irrespective of the mean stress level. It is hoped that when all such information (extension range vs alternating stress) is available for notched as well as unnotched specimens, for 0° and 45° , some important conclusions can be drawn.

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